

D3.1 Deep review of the prospective LCA approaches and applications to bio-based and fossil-based technologies

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

CML	The CML methodology was created by the University of Leiden in the Netherlands in 2001, Centrum voor Milieukunde Leiden
FUTURA	Futura is a software interface to generate arbitrary future background databases for LCA sensitivity analyses.
IAMC	Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium
IAMs	Integrated Assessment Model
IMAGE	Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment
IMPACT	IMPACT is a method for life cycle impact assessment
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCIA	Life Cycle Impact Assessment
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
PkBudg	PkBudg is a set of climate policy scenarios
PREMISE	PRospective EnvironMental Impact AsSEssment
RCPs	Representative Concentration Pathways
ReCiPe	ReCiPe is a harmonized life cycle impact assessment method at midpoint and endpoint level
REMIND	REgional Model of Investment and Development
SSPs	Shared Socioeconomy Pathways
THEMIS	Technology Hybridized Environmental-economic Model with Integrated Scenarios
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WURST	Wurst is a python package for linking and modifying industrial ecology models, with a focus on sparse matrices in life cycle assessment.

PROJECT INFORMATION

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5	NORGES TEKNISK-NATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET	NTNU
6	BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	B4C
7	BUSINESS E-INCUBATOR GO-UP	GOUP
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE SERVICIOS Y PROMOCION FORESTAL Y DE SU INDUSTRIA DE CASTILLA Y LEON	CESEFOR
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Abstract:	This study reviews existing LCA studies that address the scaling-up of technology maturity and the projection of background datasets. It compares their approaches to identify key differences and similarities, highlight research gaps and challenges, and proposes recommendations to address them.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Biomass is a promising renewable feedstock to replace conventional fossil feedstock in several economic sectors, but some bio-based alternatives are at early stages of developments with low technology readiness level (TRL), challenging a proper assessment of their environmental impacts. The assessment of emerging bio-based technologies can be performed via future-oriented life cycle assessments (LCA), but the comparability and applicability of LCA of emerging bio-based technologies still face some challenges. Results often show inconsistent terminology, limited methodological transparency, and insufficient distinction between improvements from higher TRL and those from the background economy.

In this report, we review how 120 LCA studies modeled the scale-up of emerging technologies from lab/demo to industrial scale and projected future background scenarios. Articles are classified by: I) the terminology used to describe their analytical approach, II) the methods applied to model process inventory data and simulate higher technology readiness levels, III) the ways in which future scenarios were incorporated in the analysis, particularly regarding changes in background socioeconomic conditions, and IV) key characteristics of the analyses, such as feedstock type, TRL, industry sector to which they apply, and impact categories. The review primarily focuses on emerging bio-based technologies, which are key to a circular bioeconomy transition.

About 65% of the reviewed studies defined themselves as prospective LCA, 21% as ex-ante LCA, and 14% provide no definition. Only 46 articles specifically assess bio-based technologies, and 29 assess emerging bio-based technologies. Among the latter, there is a high predominance of emerging bio-based technologies for applications in the chemical sector. About 32% of all the prospective LCA articles assessed do not consider any variation in technology maturity (i.e., TRL) and provide no scaling-up of foreground data. Integrating LCA with Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) is the most common method to project background data within the selected prospective LCA articles, followed by ad-hoc scenarios definition and integration with background data. About 25% of the articles do not provide any background projections. The implications of future background economy are usually not considered in studies defined as ex-ante LCA. In prospective LCA articles, *premise* is the most common tool to transform the background database, and electricity is the most transformed background sector. SSP2-Baseline is the most applied scenario, followed by SSP2-2.6.

Overall, our review highlights five central aspects of the current state of future-oriented LCA for emerging bio-based technologies, which underpin the main challenges related to comparability and practical applicability: I) terminology inconsistency, with the terms of “ex-ante” and “prospective” LCA frequently used as synonymous, despite the analyses focus on different TRLs, background modifications, and position in time (present or future); II) insufficient differentiation of the main drivers influencing the results, as it is often difficult to distinguish the effects of increased technological maturity from those arising from future socioeconomic developments; III) large variability in the methods used for scale-up process inventory data across TRLs and background projections; IV) insufficient transparency when applying IAMs to transform background datasets; and V) sensitivity of prospective LCA results to the selected IAM and future scenario, as the time-intensive process of transforming background datasets restricts the ability to systematically explore the influences of alternative scenarios.

Our recommendations are both ontological and technical. First, we should reduce ambiguity and increase clarity in LCA. The term “prospective” should be used to indicate approaches that estimate effects of future changes in background and foreground inventory data due to evolutions in technologies and socio-economic systems. The term ex-ante LCA should be only used when the technology to which the LCA is applied is at an early stage of development and requires scaling-up of foreground data to simulate commercial maturity, but background processes are not necessarily modified. This means that a technology that is already mature today does not need ex-ante LCA, but it can undergo a prospective LCA. To facilitate inter-study comparability and interpretation of the results, LCA practitioners should provide a clear differentiation between changes induced by simulating technology maturity across TRLs and those from changes in background conditions, clearly describing the TRL of their system and its evolution, the scenario data in prospective LCA, or if possible future efficiency improvements in the technology are considered. In the short term, an international initiative should

be launched to harmonize terminology and methods for scaling up inventory data across TRLs and projecting future background scenarios. This effort should include clear documentation of how changes in the background economy are implemented and the development of standardized transformation protocols. Future research should also focus on expanding existing tools to include underrepresented sectors (such as chemicals) and on creating new tools that enhance the robustness of prospective LCA studies by enabling the simultaneous consideration of multiple future background databases. Overall, these recommendations aim to improve methodological consistency and strengthen the role of LCA as a decision-support tool for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers involved in sustainable technology deployment under uncertain future conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The global economy is currently mainly linear and heavily based on fossil resources. To achieve climate neutrality targets and sustainable development goals, a relevant pathway might be an alternative circular economy that relies on renewable resources. Biomass is a promising renewable feedstock to replace conventional fossil feedstocks, being largely applied in the electricity and transport sectors (e.g., bioenergy and biofuels), but it is a limited resource and already faces competition among economic sectors (e.g., electricity, fuels, cement, metals).

There is great potential to replace fossil-based products in the chemicals, construction, and textiles sectors, however, the bio-based alternatives are, in some cases, at early stages of development with low technology readiness level (TRL) and the limited knowledge about their industrial-scale performance hinders the assessment of their environmental impacts (Ögmundarson et al., 2020). Fossil-based systems are fully commercial and have been optimized for decades; thus, the performance and impacts of emerging bio-based systems cannot be fairly compared with their well-established fossil counterparts.

To accelerate the transition to a sustainable circular bioeconomy, it is essential to identify the most promising emerging bio-based products, those capable of delivering the greatest environmental benefits when implemented in the future. A life cycle assessment (LCA) can contribute to this selection by anticipating potential environmental benefits and tradeoffs before their large-scale introduction to the market and incorporating economic changes coming from future socioeconomic scenarios. The application of LCA methodology to assess emerging technologies is increasing, but the terminology used to refer to them is inconsistent (Arvidsson et al., 2023). Terms such as ex-ante LCA and prospective LCA are currently used to describe assessments that estimate life cycle impacts under future conditions, either by modeling improvements in the foreground technologies (e.g., higher conversion efficiencies or lower emission factors) or by projecting changes in background systems (e.g., power mix or technology market shares in 2040 or 2050). For example, scaling-up of technology maturity is identified as prospective LCA by Erakca et al. (2024), Maimati et al. (2023) and Sun et al. (2023), and as ex-ante LCA by Müller-Carneiro et al. (2023), Sinke et al. (2023), and Tsoy et al. (2020). The transformation of background inventory datasets to mirror future socioeconomic scenarios is referred to as prospective LCA in the works of Alaux et al. (2024) and Müller et al. (2024), but projection of background economy is not included by Müller-Carneiro et al. (2023) and Tsoy et al. (2020). There are ongoing efforts to harmonize the terminology and methodologies used in the LCA of emerging technologies and to establish a common understanding of the different approaches applied, whether in scaling up inventory data across TRLs or in projecting future changes in background scenarios (Nurdiawati et al., 2025; Arvidsson et al., 2023; Adrianto et al., 2021; van der Hulst et al., 2020). It has been suggested to simplify the terminology by merging ex-ante LCA and prospective LCA into a single term, prospective LCA, defined as “LCA that models the product system at a future point in time relative to when the study is conducted” (Arvidsson et al., 2023). However, this proposal does not fully resolve the underlying challenges. By merging conceptually distinct approaches, it obscures important methodological differences, such as whether changes in the system are driven by technological learning or by evolving socioeconomic conditions. It also fails to provide guidance on how to account for uncertainty, how to select appropriate future scenarios, or how to differentiate impacts at the unit level versus system-wide projections. As a result, simply unifying the terminology may create the illusion of standardization without addressing the practical difficulties that limit comparability and robustness in future-oriented LCA studies. Other reviews have highlighted that current terminology and methodological approaches remain too generic, creating uncertainty in how upscaled emerging technologies and future background systems are modelled (Bortoli et al., 2025; Marson et al., 2025; Nurdiawati et al., 2025). Consequently, there is still a lack of clarity on what constitutes a “prospective” LCA, how it should be implemented, and how its application differs across technology maturity levels.

In this context, a comprehensive review of existing studies is useful to address the remaining knowledge gap. Examining the terminology used, the rationale behind methodological choices, the approaches applied for future-oriented modeling, and the key characteristics of each study can clarify inconsistencies and provide a structured overview of the state of the art. Such a review allows for the identification of patterns of

methodological convergence or divergence, highlights underdeveloped approaches or underrepresented sectors, and pinpoints challenges related to uncertainty and scenario implementation. The insights gained can inform recommendations to improve harmonization, transparency, and comparability in prospective LCA studies. Ultimately, mapping current practices, gaps, and best practices supports researchers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders by providing more reliable evidence on the environmental impacts of emerging technologies, thereby guiding sustainable technological development and deployment under uncertain future conditions.

In this study, we reviewed 120 LCA studies of emerging technologies, with a special focus on emerging bio-based technologies that are key to fostering a circular bioeconomy transition. We critically examine how “ex-ante” and “prospective” LCA are applied, clarify the terminology used in future-oriented LCA, identify key methodological challenges in modeling technology scale-up and future background scenarios (including IAMs), and propose clearer terminology and transparent guidelines. The study is divided in six main sections: (1) the methodology used to review the LCA articles, (2) prospective LCA approaches and definitions applied to the reviewed articles; (3) how foreground datasets are scaled up and background datasets are projected; (4) the use of Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs); (5) discussion of main gaps and challenges, potential future developments, and potential opportunities; and (6) final remarks.

METHODOLOGY

The literature review is divided into two main parts (Figure 1). In the first part, articles on LCA of bio-based technologies were selected from the Scopus database if they include keywords such as “LCA” and “prospective,” “ex-ante,” “emerging,” “early-stage,” “lab-scale,” or “low TRL”. These terms were selected to capture studies that focused on technologies at early development stages, where life cycle impacts are uncertain and future-oriented modeling is most relevant. Studies focusing on mature or commercial-scale technologies were excluded, as the goal of this review is to examine methodologies applied specifically to emerging technologies and to understand how future-oriented LCA approaches are implemented in contexts of high technological and socioeconomic uncertainty. An expert-based literature review was performed to select other relevant LCA scientific articles beyond those on bio-based technologies. Only peer-reviewed articles published from 2015 to April 2024 were considered (e.g., no conference articles, book chapters, etc.), which is a reasonable time window given the recent introduction of future-oriented LCA. The term “future-oriented LCA” is here used when generally referring to articles that perform scaling-up of technology maturity and/or projection of life cycle inventory data to a future time.

Part II aims at understanding how the existing literature is using the term “prospective LCA” to assess emerging bio-based technologies, applying a systematic approach (Table 1). The selection process began on Scopus by identifying studies that cited Sacchi et al. (2022) (i.e., *premise*) and Mendoza-Beltran et al. (2020) (i.e., *wurst*). A filter for “articles” and “bio” was applied to retain only scientific papers addressing bio-based technologies. Then, a one-by-one screening was conducted to verify the practical application of the *premise* or *wurst* tools, excluding studies that merely discussed their theoretical or potential implementation. An additional search using the keywords “prospective life cycle assessment bio” on Scopus was performed to capture any remaining studies potentially applying the *premise* or *wurst* tools. Articles that discussed prospective LCA only conceptually, without practical application, were excluded. After the three selection steps, 25 articles were retained for further analysis.

The selected articles are then classified according to a set of relevant parameters (Table 2):

I) how LCA is defined (i.e., prospective, ex-ante). The studies applying scaling-up of technology maturity and projection of background economy that do not define themselves as “prospective” or “ex-ante” were classified using the following criteria: when only scaling-up of foreground data is performed the study was classified as “ex-ante”, when background projection is performed the study was classified as prospective;

II) how foreground datasets are scaled-up to account for higher technology maturity (i.e., process

simulation, scenarios, etc.), with an overview of the main methods and approaches used;

III) how background datasets are transformed to account for future socioeconomic scenarios (i.e., IAMs, process simulation, etc.), and, when using IAMs, for which time period, sectors, and what type of tool is applied;

V) The articles assessing emerging bio-based technologies are explored based on which sector the bio-based product belongs to, what is the type of feedstock used, what is the current TRL of the assessed technology, the impact methods and category, and the system boundaries.

The scope of the review is limited to life cycle inventory data and modelling. As such, approaches for prospective life cycle impact assessment are not included in the scope of the study.

Figure 1: Framework for the selection of scientific articles. See table below for an explanation of terminology and criteria.

Table 1: Systematic review of prospective bio-based articles

Actions	Selected articles
Step 1: premise	
• Search of articles citing Sacchi et al. (2022) on Scopus	100
• Filtration of “articles”	83
• Filtration of “bio”	24
• Filtration of practical application of <i>premise</i>	17
Step 2: wurst	
• Search of articles citing Mendoza-Beltran et al. (2020) on Scopus	139
• Filtration of “articles”	109
• Filtration of “bio”	29
• Filtration of practical application of <i>wurst</i>	17
• Removal of articles already present on <i>premise</i> search	4
Step 3: additional articles	
• Search of “prospective life cycle assessment bio” on Scopus	48
• Filtration of “articles”	34
• Filtration of practical application of prospective LCA	8
• Removal of articles already present on previous steps	4
Final selection	
Total articles	25

Table 2. Description of parameters to classify the selected articles

Classification	Options	Description
How the LCA is defined	Prospective Ex-ante	The articles are classified as “ex-ante LCA” or “prospective LCA” according to their own definition.
	No definition	Some articles perform scaling-up of foreground data and/or projection of background data, but do not define themselves as “prospective” or “ex-ante”. A suggested definition is provided: the articles are classified as “ex-ante” when only scaling of foreground data is provided, and as “prospective” when projection of background data is performed.
	Process-based calculation	Calculation using process-based methods, such as done by Piccinno et al. (2016). E.g., mass and energy balances calculated applying equations, but no simulation software.
	Process simulation	Use simulation software, such as Aspen Plus.
	Scenarios	Ad-hoc scenarios that are developed by the authors, providing a mix of technical parameters, efficiency gains, and technological improvements.
Foreground scaling-up	Scaling-up factors	Includes learning curves and scaling-up factors, such as done by Tsoy et al. (2020).
	Process-based calculations and scenarios	Combination of both.
	Scaling-up factors and scenarios	Combination of both.
	Process simulation and scenarios	Combination of both.
Background projection	Others	Includes definition provided by the articles: “engineering calculations”, “climate-induced variations”, “stoichiometry calculations”.
	No scaling-up	Studies that do not modify foreground data but define themselves as “ex-ante”.
	Process-based calculation	Calculation using process-based methods, such as Piccinno et al. (2016). E.g., mass and energy balances calculated applying equations, but no simulation software.
	Ad-hoc scenarios	Ad-hoc scenarios that are developed by the authors, providing a mix of technical parameters, efficiency gains, and technological improvements.
	Process-based calculation and scenarios	Combination of both.
	IAMs	Transformation of background dataset with outputs from IAMs.
For which period	No projection	Studies that do not provide any modification of background data but define themselves as “prospective”
	Projection of background data using IAMs	
Which scenarios	The future points in time that the assessment applies (e.g., 2030, 2050). There are a set of available scenarios on literature that provide future socioeconomic narratives, combined or not with climate policies, such as the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) (Riahi et al., 2017).	
Which IAMs	There are a set of IAMs available on literature (e.g., IMAGE and REMIND) that provide	

Tailored tool	future socioeconomic outcomes that can be integrated with LCA using tailored tools. <i>premise</i>	The transformation of background data using IAMs is often performed by these two existing open-source tools.
	<i>wurst</i>	
Background sectors	Economic sectors, e.g., energy, transport, chemicals, etc.	Which sectors are being transformed.
Bio-based technologies		
TRL information	TRL level from 1 to 9.	Current TRL of the assessed technology.
Bio-based	Biofuels, bioenergy, bio-based chemicals.	Products derived from biomass.
Emerging bio-based	Bio-based technologies below TRL 8.	Products derived from biomass that are not at commercial stage ¹ , e.g., commercial biofuels and bioenergy are not considered emerging.
LCA assessment	System boundaries	What are the functional unit and system boundaries (e.g., cradle-to-gate).
	Impact methods	What is/are the impact methods (e.g., Recipe, CML) and categories considered (e.g., climate change, eutrophication).
	Approach	Attributional or consequential.

¹This follows the European Commission definitions on Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs): https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/wp/2014_2015/annexes/h2020-wp1415-annex-g-trl_en.pdf

RESULTS

Review of prospective LCA approaches

A total of 120 scientific articles were reviewed and classified in this study (refer to Annex 1 and NTNU (2025) for full list of articles). In general, ex-ante LCA studies tend to consider only developments in the maturity of a specific technology (Cucurachi et al., 2018; Moni et al., 2020), disregarding the future developments in the technological, economic, and social systems surrounding and supporting this technology. The low TRL technologies are scaled-up to explore their environmental performance in a higher TRL and to be fairly compared to the commercial counterpart at present time (Cucurachi et al 2018; Moni et al., 2020; van der Giesen et al., 2020). In practical terms, prospective LCA compares technologies at future times, incorporating future socioeconomic changes in the surrounding systems, and can be applied for both early-stage and commercial technologies (Thonemann et al., 2020; Arvidson et al., 2018; Bruhn et al., 2023). The difference between the two approaches is that in ex-ante LCA studies a foreground system is modified to mirror upscaled technology maturity, while in prospective LCA studies a background system is modified to mirror a future projection. Combinations of the two approaches exist as well. Ex-ante and prospective LCA can converge into one common approach (Arvidsson et al., 2023; 2018) or can be kept separated as two different approaches (Souza et al., 2023; Cucurachi et al. 2018; van der Giesen et al. 2020).

About 65% of the reviewed articles are self-classified as prospective LCA and 21% as ex-ante LCA (Figure 2a), and 14% do not define themselves as neither prospective nor ex-ante LCA.

Figure 2: Classification of all selected articles as prospective or ex-ante LCA considering self-classification (a) and suggested classification, when no definition is provided (b)

Application of prospective LCA to emerging bio-based technologies

Of the 120 reviewed articles, only 46 (39%) assess bio-based technologies and 29 (24%) assess emerging bio-based technologies (Figure 3a). Most of these 46 bio-based articles (52%) are self-defined prospective, and only 33% self-defined as ex-ante LCA. Including the classification considered in this review for the studies that do not classify themselves (Figure 3b), the share of prospective and ex-ante articles increases to 57% and 43%, respectively. Usually, the transformation of background datasets is applied to commercial bio-based technologies (e.g., bioenergy and biofuels). For emerging bio-based technologies, such background transformation was uncommon. Most of the 29 emerging bio-based articles (69%) are ex-ante LCA. This includes four articles that provide no definition and were classified as ex-ante, as they all perform only scaling-up of foreground data (Figure 3b). The articles that perform prospective LCA of emerging bio-based technologies date from 2021 onwards, showing an interest on the development of a bio-based economy in the last years.

Figure 3: Classification of bio-based and emerging bio-based articles as prospective or ex-ante LCA considering self-classification (a) and suggested classification, when no definition is provided (b)

Among the 29 articles, 23 are applied to the chemical sector (Table 3), showing a high predominance of the assessment of emerging bio-based technologies for chemical applications. There is a large variety of bio-based feedstocks ranging from waste streams to lignocellulosic materials. Wood or wood residues are the feedstock for bio-based products in only five of the articles. Sucrose or lignin are feedstocks in five articles, and these compounds can be extracted from lignocellulosic feedstocks.

Table 3. Description of the emerging bio-based technologies, the economic sectors they are applied, and which feedstocks are used

ID	Emerging bio-based technology	Sector	Feedstock
Prospective LCA articles¹			
2	Mycelium based composites	Chemical and construction	Fungi
11	Microalgae biogas	Energy	Microalgae
17	Bio-based fertilizer and biogas from fish oil	Agriculture and energy	Fish oil
18	Microbial sophorolipid fermentation	Chemical, pharma, food	Waste cooking oil
21	Waste-to-PHA Biorefineries	Chemical	Organic waste
37	Biowaste-based energy	Energy	Sewage sludge
40	Emerging wood-based technologies	Chemical, construction, textile	Wood
45	Forest residues biopolymers	Chemical	Forest residues
64	Bio-based aniline	Chemical	Corn stover, sugar beet and sugarcane
Ex-ante LCA articles²			
1	Microalgae	Chemical	Microalgae
5	Lightweight boards, molded fiber parts, wood plastic composite and granulate	Chemical and construction	Wood
6	Nano-reinforced biopolymer film	Chemical	Mango residue
7	Starch films for food packaging	Chemical	Starch
8	Cultivated meat	Food	Sucrose
10	Biomass-based reduction of iron	Metal	Glycerin
11	Carbon-fiber-reinforced polymers	Chemical	Lignin
12	Microalgae	Chemical	Microalgae
13	Microalgae	Chemical	Microalgae
14	Methanol, ethanol, ammonia, glucose, di-hydroxy acetone	Energy and chemical	Wood chips, lignocellulosic, plant oil and waste oil
15	Protein from rapeseed	Food and feed	Rapeseed
16	Starch from mango kernel	Chemical	Mango residue
17	Polyethylene furanoate	Chemical	Wood and corn
18	Bio-based polybutylene	Chemical	Corn starch, sugarcane,

19	succinate Polyhydroxyalkanoates from wastewater	Chemical	and lignocellulosic Waste water
Suggested ex-ante LCA articles³			
1	Bioplastic	Chemical	Brown seaweed
10	Supercapacitor electrodes based on activated carbon from coconut shells	Energy	Coconut shells
11	Nanoparticles and nanocomposite films	Chemical	Lignin
13	Dextran	Chemical, pharma and food	Sucrose
14	Biopolymers from citrus waste	Chemical	Citrus waste

¹The ID refers to the sheet “Prospective LCA” from NTNU (2025).

²The ID refers to the sheet “Ex-ante LCA” from NTNU (2025).

³The ID refers to the sheet “No definition” from NTNU (2025).

Only 34% of the 29-emerging bio-based articles clearly define the current TRL of the technology assessed, ranging from TRL 2 to TRL 9, while the other half provide more generic information as “lab-scale”, “early development stages”, and “emerging technology” (Table 4). Only five articles provide a full cradle-to-grave assessment, the most common practice is to perform cradle-to-gate assessments, excluding comprehensive and transparent biogenic carbon accounting in the end-of-life treatment (e.g., incineration, recycling, landfilling). In four of these articles, the biogenic carbon is considered as a credit coming from the carbon uptake by the plant growth (Zuiderveen et al., 2021; Muller-Carneiro et al., 2023; Fernández-DaCosta et al., 2015; Durkin et al., 2019). Finally, most articles (72%) apply an attributional LCA modelling approach, while 21% explicitly perform a consequential assessment. However, not always the articles provide a clear definition whether they apply an attributional or consequential approach, with the choice of one method over another that largely depends on the research question at hand.

The most common impact assessment methods are ReCiPe (Huijbregts et al., 2017), CML (Guinée, 2002), and IMPACT 2002+ (Jolliet et al., 2003) (Table 5), but in varying versions (e.g., ReCiPe 2008 and ReCiPe 2016, CML 2001 and CML 2016). Climate change impacts are the most common category to be explored, followed by eutrophication (includes marine and freshwater) and energy demand.

Table 4. Description of the TRL information, system boundaries and LCA approach of the emerging bio-based articles

Classification	Prospective LCA TRL information	Ex-ante LCA
TRL informed	5	5
Lab-scale	2	5
Low TRL	1	4
Not informed	0	2
Lab-scale and pilot scale	1	1
Pilot scale	0	1
Emerging technology	0	1
Early development stages	0	1
N/A	0	0
Total	9	20
System boundaries		
Cradle-to-gate	6	17
Cradle-to-grave	3	2
Others	0	1
Total	9	20
LCA approach		
Attributional	7	16
Consequential	2	4
Total	9	20

Table 5. Most used impact methods, indicators and categories of the emerging bio-based articles

Classification	Prospective Impact methods ¹	Ex-ante
ReCiPe	4	14
IMPACT	2	7
CED	0	6
IPCC	1	3
ILCD	0	1
CML	3	0
	Impact categories ²	
Climate change	3	11
Eutrophication	3	8
Energy demand	0	8
Acidification	2	6
Ecotoxicity	1	4
Toxicity	3	4
Resource use	0	1
Ozone	3	2
Land use	1	2

¹This represents the number of times each method was used; some articles use more than one method. Different versions of each method are used; no differentiation is provided here.

³This represents the number of times each category was used, some articles use more than one category, others don't list the categories. The categories are aggregated e.g., "climate change" includes global warming potential, "eutrophication", includes marine and freshwater eutrophication.

Scaling-up of foreground data and projection of background data

The scaling-up of foreground data of emerging technologies can be done applying process-based simulation and calculation (Piccinno et al., 2016), by defining scenarios from experts' interviews (Tsoy et al., 2020; Bruhn et al., 2023), scenario ranges (Cucurachi et al., 2018), patent analysis (Spreafico et al., 2023), applying scaling factors and learning curves (van der Hulst et al., 2020), and using unpublished laboratory results (Arvidsson et al., 2018).

Around 69% of the prospective LCA articles scale-up the foreground data, the most common method is to use scenarios (29%) (Table 6). However, 31% of all the assessed prospective LCA articles do not consider any variation on technology maturity (i.e., TRL) and provide no scaling-up of foreground data; focusing on the articles on emerging-bio based products, 90% of the prospective LCA articles provide scaling-up of the emerging bio-based technology, applying ad-hoc scenarios and process-based calculation (e.g., applying equations) are the two most common methods to scale-up technology maturity.

For ex-ante LCA articles, 96% of the articles scale-up the foreground data, with a range of methods applied, including their own tool/method (30%), process-based calculation (26%), scenarios (22%), and process simulation (e.g., applying simulation software) (11%). This same trend applies for emerging bio-based articles, but the shares are 32%, 26%, 21% and 11%, respectively. Only one ex-ante LCA article does not provide scaling-up of foreground data (Hesser et al., 2023) whose study self-defines as ex-ante LCA but provides a comparison of different low TRL technologies at the same maturity level.

Table 6: Methods applied by the selected articles to scale-up foreground data

How foreground data is scaled-up	All articles				Emerging bio-based articles			
	Self-definition		Suggested definition		Self-definition		Suggested definition	
	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA
No Scenarios	20	1	5	0	1	1	0	0
Process-based calculation	21	2	2	4	3	2	0	2
Others*	7	4	0	3	3	4	0	1
Process-based calculations and scenarios	14	8	0	0	1	6	0	0
Scaling-up factors	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Process simulation	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Process simulation and scenarios	1	2	1	2	1	1	0	2
Scaling-up factors and scenarios	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
	71	19	8	9	9	15	0	5

*Their own tool, engineering calculations, climate-induced variations, stoichiometry calculations.

The projection of background databases can be performed by using scenarios (Arvidsson et al., 2018; Thonemann et al., 2020) and integrating LCA background datasets with future technological changes modelled by the IAMs community (Joyce and Bjorklund, 2022; Sacchi et al., 2019; Mendoza-Beltran et al., 2020).

Integrating LCA with IAMs is the most common method (43%) to project background data within the selected prospective LCA articles (Table 7), followed by ad-hoc scenarios (26%). However, 20 articles (26%) do not provide any background inventory projection. One article conducts a prospective LCA without performing a projection of background data, as it focuses on a prospective impact assessment (Lucas et al., 2023). Of the remaining 19 articles, 17 provide only scaling-up of foreground data, while two do not perform any scaling-up of foreground data nor projection of background data. These two articles assess emerging technologies, but only at their current maturity level (Civancik-Uslu et al., 2021; Matin and Falanagan, 2024).

As for ex-ante LCA, the implications of future background economy are usually not considered and 85% of the articles do not perform any projection of background data. 15% of articles that transform the background dataset apply ad-hoc scenarios, that are not the ones used by IAMs. No ex-ante LCA study uses IAMs, and this can be considered restricted to prospective LCA assessments. From the total 29 research articles of emerging bio-based technologies, only four apply IAMs to project background data (del Oso et al., 2023; Sander-Titgemeyer et al., 2023; Souza et al., 2023; Alaux et al., 2024), meaning this practice is not widespread among assessments of low TRL technologies.

Table 7: Methods applied by the selected articles to project background data

How background data is projected	All articles				Emerging bio-based articles			
	Self-definition		Suggested definition		Self-definition		Suggested definition	
	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA	Prospective LCA	Ex-ante LCA
IAMs	33	0	1	0	4	0	0	0
No	19	15	1	9	4	12	0	5
Scenarios	15	3	6	0	1	2	0	0
Others*	3	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Process-based calculation	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Process-based calculation and scenarios	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	71	19	8	9	9	15	0	5

* Their own tool and one article (Thonemann et al., 2024) that generates a prospective dataset, thus no projection per se is provided.

The use of IAMs in prospective LCA assessments: tools, scenarios, and transformed sectors

The Integrated Assessment Modelling Consortium (IAMC, n.d.) define the IAMs as “*simplified representations of complex physical and social systems, focusing on the interaction between economy, society and the environment.*” The IAMs are integrated with a set of five future socioeconomic narratives, the so-called SSPs, that combine socioeconomic and environmental changes in the future (O’Neil et al., 2017; Riahi et al., 2017), and can be integrated with climate change policies as the Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (Riahi et al., 2017) and the Nationally Determined Contributions in the Paris Agreements (Roelfsema et al., 2020). The transformation of background datasets using IAMs projections has become increasingly common in recent years after the development of open-access tools that provide an automated transformation, such as *premise* (Sacchi et al., 2022) and *wurst* (Mendoza-Beltran et al., 2020). *Premise* was built upon the *wurst* framework (Sacchi et al., 2022) and detailed information about versions, included scenarios, updates, etc., can be found on the *premise* webpage <https://github.com/polca/premise>.

Currently, *premise* and *wurst* can be integrated with the IAMs IMAGE and REMIND and most articles (47%) chose IMAGE’s outputs to transform the background database (Table 8), while only four articles perform transformation with both IAMs (Maes et al., 2023; Zhang et al., 2024; Schmidt and Laner, 2023; Bisinella et al., 2023). Roughly 79% of the articles apply *premise* to transform the background database. SSP2 was the first narrative to be included in *premise* transformations, and just recently SSPs 1 and 5 were included, but only when choosing REMIND. This is reflected by the large use of SSP2-Baseline as future narrative (Table 9), followed by SSP2-2.6 (i.e., combined with RCP 2.6). *Premise* focuses mostly on transforming the power, cement, steel, transport, and fuel sectors, that are the most energy-intensive and carbon-emitting sectors of the economy. Consequently, electricity inventory is by far the most transformed background sector, followed by cement and transport (Table 10). Some other sectors are transformed either by adapting *premise* or proving additional modifications externally to *premise* add-ons, which is the case for user-defined scenarios for improving the representation of cobalt (van der Oever et al., 2023) and ammonia technologies (Boyce et al., 2024).

Table 8: IAMs and tools applied to transform background data

Prospective LCA	All articles		Emerging bio-based articles
	Self-definition	Suggested definition	Self-definition
	IAMS		
IMAGE	15	1	2
REMIND	12	0	1
IMAGE and REMIND	4	0	0
No information	2	0	1
Total	33	1	4
	Tools		
<i>premise</i>	27	1	3
<i>wurst</i>	7	0	1
<i>premise and wurst</i>	1	0	0
Total	33	1	4

Table 9: Future socioeconomic scenarios applied to the projection of background data

Scenarios*	All articles		Emerging bio-based articles	
	<i>premise</i>	<i>wurst</i>	<i>premise</i>	<i>wurst</i>
SSP1-Baseline	0	1	0	0
SSP1-2.6	0	1	0	0
SSP1-PkBudg500	1	0	0	0
SSP2-Baseline	15	8	1	1
SSP2-6.0	2	0	0	0
SSP2-2.6	12	5	2	1
SSP2-NDC	6	0	1	0
SSP2-1.9	9	0	0	0
SSP2-PkBudg900	4	0	0	0
SSP2-PkBudg500	1	0	0	0
SSP2-PkBudg1150	1	0	0	0
SSP3-Baseline	0	1	0	0
SSP3-3.4	0	1	0	0

*This represents the number of times each scenario was used; some articles consider more than one scenario.

Table 10: Transformed economic sectors

Sectors*	All articles	Emerging bio-based articles
Electricity	29	4
Transport	9	2
Cement	8	1
Clinker	3	0
Fuels	8	2
Steel	8	1
Materials	5	0
Energy	3	0
Hydrogen	3	0
Fleet	2	0
Metals	2	0
Batteries	1	0
Aviation	1	0
Ammonia	1	0
Cobalt	1	0

* This represents the number of times each sector was transformed; some articles transform into more than one sector.

DISCUSSION

Main research gaps and challenges

Overall, we identified five main aspects as sources of divergence in the literature of future-oriented LCA studies. They are the following:

I) **Terminological inconsistency.** The definitions of ex-ante and prospective LCA are often unclear, contrasting, and sometimes overlapping, and lack of differentiation of technology maturity (e.g., technology readiness level) from temporal position (e.g., position in time: present or future). This lack of terminological clarity prevents consistent interpretation of scope and assumptions e.g., whether a study labelled as prospective refers to low TRL, future background scenarios, or both. Such ambiguity leads to incomparable results across studies that may in fact assess different system boundaries, time horizons, or modelling assumptions. This creates confusion, limits comparability and ultimately the usefulness of such assessments.

II) **Insufficient differentiation of impact sources contributing to LCA results.** The effects of technological improvements are often not clearly separated from those of background socioeconomic changes, hindering result interpretation. To ensure clarity, studies should explicitly distinguish between impacts arising from technology maturity (TRL evolution) and those linked to future socioeconomic and environmental **developments**. Since technology developers can directly influence the evolution of technology maturity but have no control over broader socioeconomic trajectories, which happen outside system boundaries, clearly differentiating these impact sources is crucial to identify responsibilities and mitigation opportunities. Such differentiation should be reflected not only in the terminology adopted but also in the methodological approach used to structure and interpret LCA results.

III) **Limited methodological transparency.** Variability in methods used to scale-up the technology maturity and to modify the future background system. Currently, several methodological approaches are found both in the prospective and ex-ante LCA literature (i.e., scenarios, scaling factors, integrated, process simulations, etc.), hindering the robustness and comparability of the assessments.

IV) **Limited transparency for the application of IAMs to project background data.** The integration of IAMs with LCA is increasing but still needs improvement and lacks a comprehensive harmonization of its main gaps when applied to emerging bio-based technologies. Currently, studies often omit detailed information about the scenarios, sectors, and geographical coverage considered, making it difficult to trace how background projections influence LCA results. Because there are no standardized protocols, each study applies different assumptions for energy mixes, technological change, and socioeconomic pathways. This inconsistency undermines the reproducibility of results, leads to divergent environmental conclusions, and ultimately reduces the reliability of prospective LCA for policy and industrial decision-making.

V) **Complexity and time-consuming efforts for background data transformation.** One major challenge not sufficiently addressed in the literature is the time-consuming nature of transforming background datasets for prospective LCA. Tools like *premise* offer partial automation, but significant manual effort is still required to align IAM output with LCA databases, especially for underrepresented sectors such as chemicals, textiles, and bio-based technologies. This includes mapping sectoral outputs and ensuring consistency across scenarios. These tasks demand expert judgment and are rarely documented in detail, which compromises transparency and reproducibility. Transforming and integrating background databases into future-oriented LCAs can be accomplished using Python-based open-source tools. However, these approaches are often time-consuming due to the data-intensive nature of background datasets and the inherent complexity of programming-based workflows. Databases typically contain thousands of activities that must be transformed within the *premise* framework, and generating multiple databases can take several hours or even days, depending on the number of integrated IAM scenarios. Considering the ongoing developments of the framework towards the inclusion of more IAMs and SSP scenarios, the computation time for exploring the whole uncertainty from the background databases can be high. Beyond computational demands, a certain level of programming expertise is required

from LCA practitioners, as database transformations are not supported by user interfaces. Additionally, conflicts between open-source Python packages may arise due to software version changes. Consequently, extra time should be allocated to troubleshoot and resolve potential software issues when implementing open-source workflows in future-oriented LCA studies.

Main recommendations for necessary developments

Definitions of “ex-ante” and “prospective” LCA

Based on the comprehensive literature review, a possible pathway to reduce ambiguity and increase clarity in LCA is to use the term prospective LCA (Figure 4) to indicate approaches to estimate effects of future changes in background due to future evolutions in technologies and socio-economic systems for a product delivery or decision that is foreseen in the future. This includes possible changes in foreground processes of already commercially mature technologies that will further develop and improve in the future (e.g., efficiency gains in conversion efficiencies or reductions in emission factors of specific pollutants from improved waste treatment options).

The term ex-ante LCA should be only used when the technology to which LCA is applied is at an early stage of development and requires scaling-up of foreground data to simulate commercial maturity, but background processes are not necessarily modified. This means that technology that is already mature today does not need ex-ante LCA.

The terms "ex-ante" and "prospective LCA" should not be used for assessments that do not involve scaling-up of technology maturity or projection of background data. Even for emerging technologies at low TRL or early stages of development, such assessments remain conventional LCA.

A clear distinction can be sometimes challenging, and we thus recommend that practitioners provide a description of the TRL of their system, the technology maturity improvements of the foreground (if any), and how changes in the background economy are implemented (e.g., *premise* or any other tool).

Figure 4: Definition of ex-ante and prospective LCA, adapted from Souza et al. (2023) and Thonemann et al. (2020).

*Technically possible, but not usual.

Clarifying Technology Maturity and Temporal Position

To improve the interpretability of future-oriented LCA studies, it is essential to clearly distinguish between environmental impacts arising from technological maturity improvements and those resulting from changes in the background economy, that happen outside the system boundaries. This requires consistent reporting of TRLs and transparent documentation of whether and how foreground and background systems are modified. Despite dealing with low-TRL technologies, approximately 40% of reviewed articles omit TRL information, limiting reproducibility and comparability. We recommend that all studies explicitly report TRL, describe the scaling methods used, and clarify the temporal positioning of the technology within the assessment. This will enable practitioners to isolate performance gains due to technological development from those driven by socioeconomic evolution, thereby enhancing the robustness of environmental conclusions.

Harmonization of methods to scale-up TRL and to project future socioeconomic evolutions

The diversity of methods used to scale-up technologies and project future scenarios introduces significant variability across studies. To address this, we propose an international harmonization initiative involving LCA experts, process engineers, and technology developers. This effort should aim to standardize approaches for scaling technologies across TRL stages and for integrating future socioeconomic scenarios into LCA models. Such harmonization would improve comparability across technologies and sectors and facilitate the development of reproducible and policy-relevant assessments. In particular, the initiative should promote best practices for combining process simulations, scaling factors, and scenario modeling tools, ensuring methodological transparency and alignment with real-world technology development pathways.

Reducing complexity in background dataset transformation with IAMs

Transforming IAM outputs into LCA-compatible background datasets remains a time-consuming and challenging process. To streamline this, we recommend the development of standardized transformation protocols, including sector mapping templates, and scenario alignment guides. Expanding tools like *premise* to cover underrepresented sectors, such as chemicals, textiles, construction, and bio-based systems, would reduce manual effort and broaden applicability. Modular, open-source libraries could automate common transformation tasks, improving efficiency and consistency. Studies should also include detailed metadata documenting IAM sources, scenario assumptions, sectoral coverage, and manual modifications. Some advances are happening in the plastic sector (Stegmann et al., 2023), but so far, they are not incorporated into prospective LCA. Cross-disciplinary working groups involving IAM developers, LCA practitioners, and database curators are needed to foster shared understanding and methodological alignment. Finally, benchmarking studies comparing transformation approaches on common case studies would help identify best practices and quantify variability, supporting the scalability of prospective LCA for industrial and policy applications.

Tool to simultaneously consider multiple databases

As previously discussed, the high number of IAM-based prospective background databases and the data-intensive nature of transforming datasets with thousands of activities pose challenges related to both computational time and the need for programming expertise. Addressing these challenges is essential to foster the wider adoption of prospective LCA among practitioners and to enable the generation of comparable, future-oriented studies. A promising solution lies in the development of a unified and user-friendly framework that streamlines the creation, transformation, and use of prospective databases. Such a platform can integrate both foreground and background data within a single environment, allowing users to host and manage multiple background databases simultaneously. This would facilitate the consistent comparison of results across various IAM–SSP–RCP combinations without requiring extensive programming intervention. To reduce computational burdens, the framework could incorporate automated workflows, parallel processing, and cloud-based computation, significantly decreasing database generation time. Furthermore, embedding version control and dependency management would minimize conflicts among open-source Python packages, ensuring smoother updates and higher software stability over time. In addition, integrating statistical tools for uncertainty analysis

would enable practitioners to systematically evaluate the variability introduced by different climate policy storylines. Ideally, the framework would also include prospective characterization factors for impact assessment, allowing the entire LCA workflow (from inventory creation to impact assessment) to be conducted within the same platform. Overall, such an integrated, automation-oriented, and interface-based solution would promote a more consistent, efficient, and accessible approach to conducting future-oriented LCAs, reducing both computational and technical barriers for practitioners.

Additional recommendations

Assessment of emerging bio-based technologies

The assessment of emerging bio-based technologies faces some additional challenges. Bio-based products can have the same structure and/or properties as their fossil counterparts (i.e., drop-in), but also deliver new functionalities and services (i.e., dedicated). This hinders the functionality definition (Moni et al., 2020; Sampaio et al., 2023; Van der Giesen et al., 2020). Often, the assessments offer limited boundaries (i.e., usually cradle-to-gate) (Blanco-Cejas et al., 2023; Sampaio et al., 2023; van der Giesen et al., 2020), and have high uncertainty levels (Blanco-Cejas et al., 2023; Moni et al., 2020; Sampaio et al., 2023; Thonemann et al., 2020; Van der Giesen et al., 2020). For bio-based systems that are at early development stages, data availability and quality can be a challenge (Blanco-Cejas et al., 2023; Moni et al., 2020; Sampaio et al., 2023; Thonemann et al., 2020; van der Giesen et al., 2020).

These challenges hinder the robustness of the LCA assessment and the results comparability with other technologies. The recommendation is to address the multifunctionality of the products, providing a comprehensive description of the reference system (usually fossil), consider cradle-to-grave boundaries, including end-of-life impacts and detailed description of how biogenic carbon is accounted for, and be clear about data availability and uncertainty within the assessment.

Prospective Impact Assessment

The IAMs were built focusing on climate change impacts, but including other environmental impacts, as pollution, toxicity, etc., is key in the assessment of bio-based chemicals and textiles. Prospective LCA assessments should cover more than climate change impacts, ideally with characterization factors that are updated considering future background conditions.

The consideration of future effects on environmental impact characterization, e.g. as done for water scarcity by Baustert et al. (2022), and for biodiversity loss (Lucas et al., 2023) has been worked out far less in literature but can also be included in the prospective LCA definition.

Dynamic impacts

Another challenge in the assessment of bio-based technologies is that processes and impacts are spread over time (Schaubroeck et al., 2021). In this sense, a product system can have impacts that happened in the past (e.g., carbon uptake from plant growth), present (e.g., CO₂ emissions from industrial operation) and future (e.g., end-of-life of bio-based plastics). These impacts spread over time can be integrated into prospective LCA assessments but should remain as a part of the dynamic LCA umbrella (Levasseur et al., 2010). In addition, during the life cycle impact assessment phase (LCIA), characterization factors should be further refined, as background concentrations of substances may vary across different IAM scenarios in the future (for example, changes in future CO₂ concentrations that could, in turn, alter the global warming impacts of various greenhouse gases). Therefore, adopting a dynamic and prospective approach for the LCIA is essential for future-oriented LCA studies.

FINAL REMARKS

This study reviewed and classified 120 scientific articles of future-oriented LCA. About 65% of them are self-defined as prospective LCA, 21% are self-defined ex-ante LCA, while 14% provide no definition. Only 29 articles assess emerging bio-based technologies, mostly applied to the chemical sector, calling for more future-oriented research of emerging bio-based chemicals.

Integrating LCA with IAMs is the most common method to project background data, followed by ad-hoc and/or self-elaborated scenarios. However, 25% of self-defined prospective LCA articles do not perform background projection. The implications of future background economy are usually not considered in ex-ante LCA studies, and the use of IAMs is restricted to prospective ones. Among the emerging bio-based technologies, the transformation of background datasets using IAMs is not widespread.

There is currently a high level of ambiguity in the definitions of ex-ante and prospective LCA, which is only partially amended by recent harmonization efforts. A clearer understanding can stem by using the term prospective LCA to only indicate approaches that estimate effects of future changes in background inventory data due to evolutions in technologies and socio-economic systems. The term ex-ante LCA should be only used when the technology to which LCA is applied is at an early stage of development and requires scaling-up of foreground data to simulate commercial maturity, but background processes are not necessarily modified. Assessments without variations in technology maturity and temporal position belong to the category of conventional LCA.

Greater transparency is needed to clearly distinguish environmental impacts arising from technological maturity improvements from those driven by changes in the background economy that occur outside system boundaries. This distinction would allow practitioners to isolate performance gains due to technological development from those resulting from socioeconomic evolution, thereby enhancing the robustness and interpretability of environmental conclusions.

The wide diversity of methods currently used to scale up technologies and project future scenarios introduces significant variability across studies. To address this, we propose an international harmonization initiative involving LCA experts, process engineers, and technology developers. This effort should aim to standardize approaches for scaling technologies across TRL stages and for consistently integrating future socioeconomic scenarios into LCA models.

Transforming IAM outputs into LCA-compatible background datasets remains a time-consuming and technically challenging process. To streamline this, we recommend developing standardized transformation protocols, including sector mapping templates and scenario-alignment guides. Expanding tools such as *premise* to cover underrepresented sectors, such as chemicals, textiles, construction, and bio-based systems, would further reduce manual effort and broaden applicability, supporting more comprehensive and comparable prospective LCAs. Additionally, prospective LCAs face challenges due to the computational intensity of transforming large IAM-based background databases, the need for programming expertise, and potential conflicts among open-source Python packages. Addressing these barriers related to transforming large IAM-based background databases is key to enabling consistent, comparable future-oriented studies. A unified, user-friendly framework integrating foreground, background, and impact assessment data could streamline workflows, reduce computation time, and minimize technical difficulties. Incorporating automated processing, version control, and uncertainty analysis would further enhance efficiency and reliability, ultimately promoting broader adoption and harmonization of prospective LCAs across diverse climate and policy scenarios.

Harmonizing scaling-up methods and how to project background data using IAMs is urgent, as these approaches can be instrumental to identify the most practical and promising solutions to decarbonize our fossil economy, especially considering the potential increased future competition for limited biomass resources. The selection of promising emerging bio-based technologies requires sustainability-driven innovation to guide their development and improving the prospective LCA methodology and application is a key tool to achieve this.

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ANNEX 1: LIST OF 120 REVIEWED ARTICLES

ID*	Authors
Prospective LCA articles	
1	(Accardo et al., 2024)
2	(Alaux et al., 2024)
3	(Bisinella et al., 2024)
4	(Boyce et al., 2024)
5	(Cavalett et al., 2024)
6	(Estévez et al., 2024)
7	(Fraga et al., 2024)
8	(Kamali et al., 2024)
9	(Matin & Flanagan, 2024)
10	(Müller et al., 2024)
11	(Romagnoli et al., 2024)
12	(Thonemann, Pierrat, et al., 2024)
13	(Thonemann, Saavedra-Rubio, et al., 2024)
14	(Wei et al., 2024)
15	(Zhang et al., 2024)
16	(Adrianto et al., 2023)
17	(Arfelli et al., 2023)
18	(Balina et al., 2023)
19	(Ballal et al., 2023)
20	(Blume et al., 2024)

21	(Saavedra del Oso et al., 2023)
22	(Douziech et al., 2024)
23	(Gallego Dávila et al., 2023)
24	(Georgiades et al., 2023)
25	(Graupner et al., 2023)
26	(Grenz et al., 2023)
27	(Heiho et al., 2023)
28	(Hermansson et al., 2023)
29	(Iturrondobeitia et al., 2023)
30	(Kamali et al., 2023)
31	(Krishnan et al., 2024)
32	(Lamers et al., 2023)
33	(Langkau et al., 2023)
34	(Maes et al., 2023)
35	(Maimaiti et al., 2023)
36	(Ostermann et al., 2023)
37	(Porcelli et al., 2023)
38	(Rodrigues et al., 2023)
39	(Rossi et al., 2023)
40	(Sander-Titgemeyer et al., 2023)
41	(Viveros Santos et al., 2023)
42	(Schmidt & Laner, 2023)
43	(Schulte et al., 2023)

44	(Šimaitis et al., 2023)
45	(Souza et al., 2023)
46	(Spreafico et al., 2023)
47	Sun et al., 2023
48	(Terlouw et al., 2023)
49	(van den Oever et al., 2023)
50	(Watanabe et al., 2023)
51	(Weidner et al., 2023)
52	(Weyand et al., 2023)
53	(Wickerts et al., 2023)
54	(Wickerts et al., 2024)
55	(Adrianto & Pfister, 2022)
56	(Baustert et al., 2022)
57	(Cavalett et al., 2022)
58	(Joyce & Björklund, 2022)
59	(Lai et al., 2022)
60	(Watanabe et al., 2022)
61	(S. Zhang et al., 2022)
62	(Civancik-Uslu et al., 2021)
63	(Morfeldt et al., 2021)
64	(Winter et al., 2021)
65	(Cox et al., 2020)
66	(van der Hulst et al., 2020)

67	(Azzi et al., 2019)
68	(Thonemann & Schulte, 2019)
69	(Mendoza Beltran et al., 2020)
70	(Porcelli et al., 2023)
71	(Manda et al., 2015)
Ex-ante LCA articles	
1	(Jouannais et al., 2024)
2	(Molinari et al., 2024)
3	(Santiago-Herrera et al., 2024)
4	(Eltohamy et al., 2023)
5	(Linser et al., 2023)
6	(Müller-Carneiro, Figueirêdo, et al., 2023)
7	(Müller-Carneiro, Rodrigues, et al., 2023)
8	(Sinke et al., 2023)
9	(Tsoy et al., 2023)
10	(Xu et al., 2023)
11	(Abbate et al., 2022)
12	(Jouannais et al., 2022)
13	(Jouannais & Pizzol, 2022)
14	(Karka et al., 2022)
15	(Röder et al., 2022)
16	(Pereira da Silva et al., 2021)
17	(Zuiderveen et al., 2021)
18	(Tecchio et al., 2016)
19	(Fernández-Dacosta et al., 2015)
Not defined as ex ante or prospective LCA articles	

1	(Ayala et al., 2024)
2	(Han et al., 2024)
3	(Materazzi et al., 2024)
4	(Ohms et al., 2024)
5	(Istrate et al., 2023)
6	(Leão et al., 2023)
7	(Lucas et al., 2023)
8	(Zacharopoulos et al., 2023)
9	(C. Zhang et al., 2023)
10	(Glogic et al., 2022)
11	(Rivière et al., 2021)
12	(Bartolozzi et al., 2020)
13	(Ahmadi et al., 2019)
14	(Durkin et al., 2019)
15	(De Morais Lima et al., 2019)
16	(Van der Voet et al., 2019)

17	(Yao et al., 2015)
Review articles	
1	(Erakca et al., 2024)
2	(Arvidsson et al., 2024)
3	(Blanco-Cejas et al., 2023)
4	(Bruhn et al., 2023)
5	(Sampaio et al., 2023)
6	(Adrianto et al., 2021)
7	(Moni et al., 2020)
8	(Thonemann et al., 2020)
9	(Tsoy et al., 2020)
10	(van der Giesen et al., 2020)
11	(Buyle et al., 2019)
12	(Arvidsson et al., 2018)
13	Cucurachi et al., 2018 Ex-ante LCA of Emerging technologies☆

*IDs refer to the “Prospective LCA”, “Ex-ante LCA”, “No definition” and “Literature review”, respectively, from NTNU (2025).

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